

ROLE OF VASA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF RAKTAPITTA: A LITERARY REVIEW**Dr. Akanksha Bharmaria^{*1}, Dr. Vividha Mahant², Dr. Upasna³, Dr. Dipsha Chauhan⁴**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda the science of life give emphasis on maintenance of health. According to *Ayurveda*, Health of individual depends on the balance between *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Mala*. *Raktapitta* is a bleeding disorder in which *Rakta* gets vitiated by *Pitta* and flows out of the external openings of body. *Vyadhi* is called *Raktapitta* because *Pitta* combines with *Rakta* and vitiates *Rakta* and also because it acquires the smell and colour of the *Rakta*. In *Ayurveda*, *Charaka Acharya* described the use of *Vasa* in *Raktapitta chikitsa*. *Vasa* is a well-known herbal drug in *Ayurvedic* system of medicines and it is found throughout the year. It balances the vitiated *Pitta* and *Rakta* and thus act as *Samprapti Vighatan*. *Vasa*'s *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipaka* balance vitiated *Pitta* and *Rakta*. Among numerous drugs mentioned in management of *Raktapitta*, *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.) is considered as the best drug of choice. Hence this article summarizes the role of *Vasa* in management of *Raktapitta*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Raktapitta*, *Vasa*, Bleeding.**INTRODUCTION**

Raktapitta as described in *Ayurvedic* classics, refers to vitiation of *Rakta* and *Pitta dosha*, leading to bleeding disorders.^[1] The disease is often compared with modern bleeding conditions like epistaxis, hematemesis, hemoptysis, hematuria etc.

Vasa is a prominent *Ayurvedic* herb traditionally used for bleeding disorders, respiratory ailments and *Pitta* related conditions. It is mentioned in various classical texts for its efficacy in controlling bleeding, cooling excessive *Pitta* and healing tissues.

Raktapitta is a serious disease and quick acting disease as similar to fire, it manifests by itself and affect rapidly. Therefore the physician who is well versed in the etiology, signs and symptoms of this disease, should immediately take steps for its treatment.^[2]

This article elaborates the role of *Vasa* in the management of *Raktapitta* from an *Ayurvedic* and pharmacological perspective.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the concept of *Raktapitta* as described in *Ayurvedic* classical texts.
2. To study the role of *Vasa* in the management of *Raktapitta* based on *Ayurvedic* literature.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This article content is compiled from *ayurvedic* text (*Charaka Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya* along with their *Teekas*), *Raj Nighantu*, *Bhavprakash*, *API* and authentic books.

Causes of *Raktapitta*^[3]

Ahara Hetu: Excessive consumption of *Ushana*, *Ati teekshan*, *Amla*, *Lavana Ahara*. Consumption of oily, deep fried foods.

1. **Vihara Hetu:** Excessive exposure to sun and heat. Staying awake at night. Overexertion (physical, mental).
2. **Seasonal factors:** More common in *Grishma* and *Sharad Ritu* when *Pitta* naturally increases.

The *Sheeta* nature of *Vasa* pacifies aggravated *Pitta*, the primary *Dosha* involved in *Raktapitta*.

Pharmacological activities

Anti inflammatory: Aqueous and alcoholic extracts showed anti inflammatory action in rats using carrageenan induced rat paw edema model.^[16]

Bronchodilator activity: Vasicinone important alkaloid exhibited powerful bronchodilator action both in normal and histamine induced bronchoconstriction in guinea pig's lungs. Aerosol inhalation of alkaloids of *Adhatoda vasica* at 10 mg/ml exhibited significant protection against allergen induced bronchoconstriction.^[17]

Antiulcer: In ethanol and aspirin induced ulcer model of rats, treatment with *adhatoda* leave extract exhibited significant antiulcer activity in experimental animals. Results were better in ethanol induced ulceration model.^[18]

Dose^[19]: 10-20 ml Of juice of fresh leaves.
10 -20 g of the dried drug for decoction.

Formulations and usage: *Ayurveda* describes various dosage forms of *Vasa* such as *Swarasa*, *Avaleha*, *Ghrta* – used in different bleeding disorders. *Charaka* and other classical texts cite *Vasa* especially in *Vasa Ghrta*, which is used internally for managing *Raktapitta*. This *Vasa Ghrta* taken along with honey to stop bleeding immediately.^[20]

Clinical relevance: *Vasa*'s role extends beyond *Pitta* pacification to healing ulcers and controlling bleeding across multiple sites, making it mainstay herb in managing *Raktapitta*. It helps restore the equilibrium of *Rakta Dhatu* and prevents recurrence by regulating the underlying *Dosha* imbalance.

DISCUSSION

The present study explores the role of *Vasa* in management of *Raktapitta*, a classical bleeding disorder described in *Ayurveda*. *Raktapitta* is primarily a *Pitta Pradhana* disease characterized by vitiation of *Rakta* and *Pitta Dosha*. *Vasa* has been highlighted as one of the most potent herbs in ayurvedic pharmacology for its *Pittashamaka*, *Raktstambhaka* and *Shothahara* properties. *Vasa* among the prime herbs used in disorders of bleeding due to its *Tikta*, *Kshaya* and *Sheeta Veerya*.

Furthermore, the mucolytic and bronchodilatory effects of *Vasa*, support its traditional usage in upper gastrointestinal and respiratory forms of *Raktapitta*.

The choice of formulation may depend upon the site and severity of the bleeding and overall strength of the patient. It is also important to note that the mode of preparation affects the pharmacokinetics and efficacy of the herb.

The integration of both classical references and modern

pharmacological studies validate the anti inflammatory, hemostatic and antioxidant properties of *Vasa*, making it a valuable therapeutic agent in the management of *Raktapitta*.

CONCLUSION

Vasa, a potent ayurvedic herb known for its hemostatic, anti inflammatory and *Pitta* pacifying properties, plays a significant role in the management of *Raktapitta*. Its efficacy in controlling bleeding, cooling the system and supporting respiratory and circulatory health aligns well with the pathophysiology of *Raktapitta* described in classical texts. By addressing both the symptoms and underlying *Dosha* imbalance, *Vasa* offers a holistic, natural approach to treatment. Incorporating *Vasa* in the therapeutic regimen, guided by proper ayurvedic principles, can thus provide effective and sustainable management of *Raktapitta*.

Vasa exemplifies an important ayurvedic medicinal plant with a comprehensive therapeutic profile suitable for *Raktapitta*, especially *Urdhvaga* type. It serves a bridge between classical ayurvedic wisdom and modern pharmacological validation.

REFERENCES

1. Sharma R. K., Dash B., *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*. Chapter -4, verse – 9, *Agnivesa's Charak samhita Chakrapani datta's Ayurveda dipika*. Chikitsa sthan. Chowkhambha sanskrit series office Varanasi, pageno, 223.
2. H. K. Shashirekha, Sushant B, *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, Chapter -4, Verse - 5, *Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthan*, Chaukhambha publications New Delhi, pageno, 242.
3. Shastri K., Chaturvedi G., *Raktapittanidan Adhyaya*, Chapter -2, Verse-4, *Charak Samhita Nidan sthan*, Chaukhambha bharti academy, Varanasi, page no, 618.
4. Shastri K., Chaturvedi G., *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, Chapter – 4, Verse – 7- 8, *Charak Samhita Chikitsa sthan*, Chaukhambha bharti academy, Varanasi, Page no, 176.
5. H. K. Shashirekha, Sushant B, *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, Chapter -4, Verse – 10, *Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthan*, Chaukhambha publications New Delhi, pageno, 244.
6. Sharma R. K., Dash B., *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, Chapter -4, Verse- 11-12. *Agnivesa's Charak samhita Chakrapani datta's Ayurveda dipika*. Chikitsa sthan. Chowkhambha sanskrit series office Varanasi, pageno, 223.
7. Sharma R. K., Dash B., *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, Chapter -4, Verse – 13- 14, *Agnivesa's Charak samhita Chakrapani datta's Ayurveda dipika*. Chikitsa sthan. Chowkhambha sanskrit series office Varanasi, pageno, 225.
8. H. K. Shashirekha, Sushant B, *Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya*, chapter – 4, verse – 25, *Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthan*. Chaukhambha publications New

- Delhi, pageno, 251.
9. Sitaram B., Raktapittaadhikar, chapter -9, verse 15, volume -II, Bhavapraksh Madhyama and uttara khanda, Chaukhambha orientalia Varanasi, Page no, 172.
 10. Shastri K., Chaturvedi G., Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya, chapter -4, verse- 88, Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthan. Chaukhambha bharti academy, Varanasi, page no, 192.
 11. Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India, part 1, volume 1. Government of India Minstry of Health and family welfare Department of Ayurveda, yoga, naturopathy, unani and homeopathy (AYUSH) New Delhi, page no, 122.
 12. Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India, part 1, volume VIII. Government of India Minstry of Health and family welfare Department of Ayurveda, yoga, naturopathy, unani and homeopathy (AYUSH) New Delhi: page no, 162.
 13. Tripathi I., Shatahvadivarga, verse 46, Raj Nighantu, Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi, page no. 71.
 14. Kushwaha H. S., Annswaroopvigyaniya Adhyaya, chapter -6, verse – 79, Ashtanga hridayam composed by Vagbhata Sarvangasundara's and Ayurvedarasayana's Kusumprabha Hindi commentary First part, Chaukhambha orientalia Varanasi, Pageno. 291.
 15. Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India, part 1, volume VIII. Government of India Minstry of Health and family welfare Department of Ayurveda, yoga, naturopathy, unani and homeopathy (AYUSH) New Delhi: page no. 162.
 16. George n et all (1947); Investigation on plant antibiotic – A search for antibiotic substance in some Indian Medicinal Planta J. Sci. Ind. Res, 2-613.
 17. Chaudry NT n et all; Effect of Adhatoda vasica on airway responsiveness with pulmonary function test, Prof. Med. J., 2006; 12(3): 327-30.
 18. Srivastava N n et all, Antiulcer activity of Adhatoda vasica Nees, J. Herb Pharmacother, 2006; 6(2): 43-49.
 19. Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India, part 1, volume 1. Government of India Minstry of Health and family welfare Department of Ayurveda, yoga, naturopathy, unani and homeopathy (AYUSH) New Delhi: page no. 122.
 20. H. K. Shashirekha, Sushant B, Raktapittachikitsa Adhyaya, chapter – 4 verse- 88, Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthan. Chaukhambha publications New Delhi, pageno. 267.